

SELECTION TEST OF NEW VARIETIES

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Abstract: Andijan-35 (2006), Andijan-36 (2009), Andijan-37 (2012), Ibrat (2011), UzPITI-202 (2021) cotton varieties created at the Andijan scientific experimental station were regionalized and included in the State Register, New UzPITI-201 (2013), UzPITI-203 (2017), SP-204 (2021) were considered to be promising, the varieties SP-206, SP-207, SP-209 created after them are being tested in the State variety testing networks, and the varieties and lines are valuable for the economy Information about the signs is provided.

Key words: cotton varieties included in the state register, cotton varieties being tested in promising and variety testing networks. Characteristics of economic value of cotton varieties.

Ottom is the national wealth of our country, and our country always pays attention to the development of this industry. Creating new varieties and introducing them to production is of great importance in the further development of cotton farming. In this regard, our breeding scientists recommend a number of new varieties for testing to the State variety testing networks every year. Among these, research is being carried out in the field of creation of new varieties and their introduction into production at PSUEAITI Andijan scientific experimental station. , Andijon-37 (2012), Ibrat (2011), UzPITI-202 (2021) were regionalized and included in the State Register, created after that are being tested in State variety testing networks. In addition, 12 new ridges were studied by the scientists of our station in 2020-2022 in the experiment "Andijon-35 V-type, Andijon-36 IV-type were planted as a model variety and the ridges were compared and studied. In the experimental area, the varieties and ridges were placed in the 4th row, in the 2nd tier, and observations were made. The cultivars and rows planted in the experiment were phenologically observed on June 1, July 1, August 1, and September 1, and 50% flowering and 50% opening periods were determined.

Agrotechnical activities were carried out based on the procedure adopted at the Andijan scientific experiment station. During the period of cotton ripening, 100 bolls of cotton were picked as a sample for laboratory analysis. Early ripening of new varieties allows harvesting the main part of the crop before frost. Therefore, the focus in the experiment was on speed. During the experiment, according to the data obtained during the period of application of cotton (Table 1), among the rows numbered 167-T, 165-T, 971-T, 8-t, 18-T, it was known that the rows ripen faster than the standard varieties.

1-Table

Valuable signs of varieties and ridges for the economy

No	Variety systems	and	Practical day	Overall percent positioning	of	Developing	Making silk	Length of silk mm

			with Vint			
1	Template-35 Andijan	128	5,0	39,5	36,8	33,1
2	Andijan-36 template	124	3,6	38,1	38,2	33,4
3	92-T	125	2,6	44,0	37,2	33,8
4	18-T	123	2,0	43,5	37,7	34,0
5	8-T	124	2,6	42,1	38,6	33,1
6	4-T	127	3,5	43,1	36,7	33,7
7	523-T	126	2,1	37,1	37,2	33,0
8	12-T	127	1,8	41,7	38,3	33,3
9	970-T	128	3,1	41,2	36,8	32,8
10	971-T	119	2,3	42,2	39,5	34,3
11	972-T	127	1,6	43,5	37,1	33,0
12	165-T	123	3,2	42,7	38,2	33,2
13	166-T	125	3,0	38,9	36,6	32,6
14	167-T	121	2,8	41,4	38,0	33,6

It was found that all ridges in the experiment were less infected than the model in terms of ridge wilt tolerance. 92-T, 971-T, 165-T, 167-T, 18-T, 8-T, 4-T, 972-T, 12-T, 970-T numbered rows of cotton harvested in September are sample varieties 10-18% higher than the yield. Cotton is grown mainly for its fiber. Therefore, the main attention was paid to the fiber output of the ridges studied in the experiment. In particular, it was found that 8-T, 12-T, 971-T, 167-T, 165-T ridges are 2-3% higher than the model variety Andijan-35, **in the experiment, fertile, early, high fiber yield and quality ridges were selected. Also, based on the above data (three-year average) and taking into account the fact that the new rows studied in the "Tanlov nav Sinish" experiment fully met the requirements of light industry in terms of fiber quality, micronaire indicators, and their valuable characteristics for the economy were superior to the standard variety, Row 167 - SP -210, 971-Tizma - under the name of SP-211, it was recommended to the State Variety Testing Commission, with the approval of the inter-organizational commission, for testing (in 2023).**

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